

**TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION, DEGREE OF BURNOUT, AND STRESS
PREVENTATIVE COPING STRATEGY: BASIS FOR DEVELOPMENT
OF MENTAL HEALTH AND PSYCHOSOCIAL SUPPORT
(MHPSS) ACTIVITIES**

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ABSTRACT

Teachers' mental health is a crucial factor in students' academic performance as it affects the teachers' ability to deliver instructions and motivate learners. This study aimed to determine the teachers' demographic profile, job satisfaction, degree of burnout, and stress-preventative coping strategies and use these as the basis for the development of Mental Health and Psychosocial Support (MHPSS) activities. This study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design; a survey questionnaire was used to collect data from 139 teachers of Kasiglahan Village Elementary School, Montalban, Rizal, Philippines. It employed a stratified random sampling technique to select a sample size of 139 teachers from the total population of 215 teachers. The study found that the teachers' job satisfaction ($M=4.03$, $SD=0.87$) is verbally interpreted as 'satisfied', the teachers' degree of burnout ($M=3.30$, $SD=2.07$) is verbally interpreted or frequently felt 'at least once a month', and the teachers' stress preventative coping strategy ($M=4.16$, $SD=0.69$) is verbally interpreted as 'agree' with the list of coping strategies provided in the questionnaire. The chi-square analyses revealed that teachers' age group is positively correlated to the level of job satisfaction ($\chi^2=.029$, $p<0.05$). These findings suggest that teachers' age group affects their overall job satisfaction; thus, schools must sustain research-based mental health activities. The school environment should build a culture that displays a high level of gratification and promotes social and emotional competency in all employees. Capitalize on intangible factors like communication, boosting confidence, respect for oneself and others, optimism, trust, problem-solving skills, coping skills, and a sense of purpose.

Keywords: *Job satisfaction, degree of burnout, stress preventative coping strategy, mental health and psychosocial support*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers' mental health is an essential aspect in students' academic performance as it boosts the teachers' aptitude to provide quality instructions and stimulate learners' critical thinking. Thus, it is important to sustain teachers' mental health and help them cope with the different stressors. In a study completed by Yale Center for Emotional Intelligence among American teachers during pandemic, it found that there were an increase in anxiety among teachers since COVID-19 pandemic and this increase was associated with balancing their families and their needs while working full-time and learning how to use technology (Yale School of Public Health, 2020). In the Philippines, although Filipino teachers demonstrated optimistic viewpoint in life amid the pandemic, psychological stress or anxiety is obvious in their lives due to the fact that their lifestyle had adjusted and they were worried about the safety of their loved ones (Talidong & Toquero, 2020).

The result of this research is envisioned to be a basis for development of mental health and psychosocial support activities, wherein the topics for the webinars are based on the perceived needs of the teachers gained through a systematic manner. The result of this study further pinpointed the most proximal contributing factor of teachers' burnout, and guides school administrators to recalibrate their course of actions in providing the needs of the teachers. It has an end view for social and educational betterment among teachers, through understanding their job satisfaction, burnout, and stress preventative coping strategy.

Legal Basis for the Implementation of Mental Health and Psychosocial Services

Every year the Schools Division of Rizal conducts a Monitoring of School Readiness to ensure the readiness of all schools in the opening of classes. The activity further aims to measure the capacity of the schools to implement and sustain the school programs despite of different adversities. For the past three years, Mental Health and Psychosocial Services (MHPSS) are included in the school readiness checklist. In the Division Memorandum No. 380, s. 2020, titled "Online Monitoring and Validation of *Oplan Balik Eskwela* (OBE), Schools Readiness and Opening of Classes for S.Y. 2020-2021", the Indicator 9 of School Readiness Checklist requires school to conduct Mental Health and Psychosocial Services. In the Division Memorandum No. 371, s. 2021, titled "Convergence on *Oplan Balik Eskwela* 2021", the Indicator 10 of School Readiness Self-assessment Checklist requires school to conduct Mental Health and Psychosocial Services for students, teachers, and non-teaching personnel. In the Division Memorandum No. 434, s. 2022, titled "Monitoring of Opening of Classes, Implementation of K-12 Basic Education Curriculum, and School Governance and Operations for School Year 2022-2023", the Indicator 4 under the support mechanism of Part II of Monitoring Tool for Opening of Classes S.Y. 2022-2023 requires schools to have provision of mental

health and psychosocial support to all personnel. For the past three years, Kasiglahan Village Elementary School was conducting webinars for Mental Health and Psychosocial Services (MHPSS). However, the topics for webinars were general in nature and there were no innovative activities that address the mental health of the teachers.

Nature of Job Satisfaction, Burnout, and Stress Preventative Coping Strategy

Job satisfaction plays an essential role in the overall commitment and productivity of the school organization (Baluyos et al. 2019). Job satisfaction affects students' performance, and educational improvement, it leads towards school improvement, quality education and student satisfaction (Maqbool, 2017). Burnout is defined as a state of physical and emotional depletion resulting from conditions of work (Whitehead, 2001). It is generally conceived to be a chronic response to extreme pressures and involves emotional exhaustion, feelings of low accomplishment and a depersonalisation of others in the work context (Maslach et al., 1996). In United States, years of teaching experience is related to teacher burnout (McCarthy et al., 2009). On the other hand, gender and academic degree do not seem to relate to teachers' burnout, however, age and years of teaching experiences were related to burnout (Croom, 2003). Preventive coping strategy may be operative in decreasing the extent of burnout among teachers who are in stressful positions (Mooney, 2018).

School environment and the teaching profession are frequently demanding, teachers are mentally and physically challenged due to extensive changes in the learning environment, instructional approaches and roles as educators (Pressley, 2021). Furthermore, the study of Pressley (2021) revealed different contributing factors in the burnout of teachers, such as anxiety in using technology and providing virtual instruction, anxiety in communicating with parents, anxiety in communicating with school administrators, lack of administrative support, and COVID-19 anxiety scale.

Research Questions

The main objective of this research study was to determine the teachers' demographic profile, job satisfaction, degree of burnout, and stress preventative coping strategy. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of teachers?
 - 1.1 sex
 - 1.2 age group
 - 1.3 educational attainment
 - 1.4 teaching position
 - 1.5 teaching experience
2. What is the level of teachers' job satisfaction?
 - 2.1 work and workplace
 - 2.2 supervisor and management
 - 2.3 benefits and recognitions

3. What is the teachers' degree of burnout?
4. What is the teachers' stress preventative coping strategy?
5. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' demographic profile and their level of job satisfaction, degree of burnout, and stress preventative coping strategy?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis that was tested in the study is: there is no significant relationship between teachers' demographic profile and their job satisfaction, degree of burnout, and stress preventative coping strategy.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Descriptive-correlational research design was utilized in this study. Primarily, it aimed at describing two or more variables and discovering the relationships that occur between or among them (Sousa et al., 2007). The design is used to describe the teachers' demographic profile, job satisfaction, degree of burnout, and stress preventative coping strategy. After describing the aforementioned variables, the study tested if there is significant correlation between the independent variable and the dependent variables.

Respondents or Sources of Data

The respondents of this study were one hundred thirty-nine (139) teachers from kindergarten, SPED, grades 1 to 6. The inclusion criteria for the teachers-respondents are the following: must be a permanent teacher in Kasiglahan Village Elementary School, and must voluntarily participate in answering the research questionnaire.

Sampling Technique

This research employed stratified random sampling technique to select a sample size of one hundred thirty-nine (139) teachers from the total population of two hundred fifteen (215) teachers. The teachers' grade level served as their strata. With the stratified random sampling, there is an equal chance or probability of selecting each unit from a group of the population (Etikan & Bala, 2017).

The definitive calculation for the number of respondents was obtained with the use of Raosoft online sample size calculator. To calculate the parameters, statistics was set to: alpha error of probability of 5%; confidence level (1- β error prob) of 95%; population size of 215; and a response distribution of 50%. It yielded a required sample size of 139.

Scope and Limitation

The study was conducted during the School Year 2022-2023 at Kasiglahan Village Elementary School. The scope of the study is delimited to determination of teachers' demographic profile, job satisfaction, degree of burnout, and stress preventative coping strategy, and exploring the relationship among them. The teachers' demographic profile is delimited to sex, age group, educational attainment, teaching position, and teaching experience. The dimensions of teachers' job satisfaction are delimited to: work and workplace, supervisor and management, and benefits and recognitions.

As to limitation, this research covered only one locale of the study, however, the number of teachers is in Mega category with two hundred fifteen (215) teachers. The majority of the sex of the teachers is also female.

Data Gathering Method

A survey data collection was chosen for the current study to collect quantitative data from the respondents. A survey instrument was carried out in order to address the main research questions. The use of a Likert-type scale improved the data collection process and analysis of teachers' job satisfaction, degree of burnout, and preventative coping strategy. The rationale for using a survey data collection was to generalize a population in order to make inferences about their characteristics (Creswell, 2007).

The research instrument is combination of researcher-made and standardized scale. The first part of the instrument is about the demographic profile of the teachers, the second part is the job satisfaction survey (NACCHO, 2012), the third part is the burnout inventory (Maslach et al., 1996), and the fourth part is the stress preventative coping strategy (McCarthy et al., 2014).

Data Analysis

The researcher imported the raw data to **PSPP software**, it is an open-source application used for statistical analysis of sampled data. Several statistical formulae were used to answer the statement of the problem in this study.

To analyse the data in problem no. 1 "What is the demographic profile of teachers?" – **frequency** and **percentage** were used.

To analyse the data in problem no. 2 "What is the level of teachers' job satisfaction?", problem no. 3 "What is the teachers' degree of burnout?" and problem no. 4 "What is the teachers' stress preventative coping strategy?" – **mean**, and **standard deviation** were used.

To analyse the data in problem no. 5 "Is there a significant relationship between teachers' demographic profile and their level of job satisfaction, degree of burnout, and stress preventative coping strategy?" – **Chi-square** was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Teachers

Table 1.1
Sex of Teachers

Sex	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	15	10.79
Female	124	89.21
Total	139	100.0%

The table 1.1 shows that out of one hundred thirty-nine (139) teachers, 10.79% are male (f=15) and 89.21% are female (f=124).

Table 1.2
Age Group of Teachers

Age Group	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
20-25	6	4.32
26-30	28	20.14
31-35	18	12.95
36-40	28	20.14
41-45	20	14.39
46-50	16	11.51
51-55	14	10.07
56-60	8	5.76
61+	1	0.72
Total	139	100.0%

As shown in table 1.2, the highest numbers of respondents are in the age groups of 26-30 years old and 36-40 years old (f=28) or 20.14%. On the other hand, lowest numbers of respondents falls under the age group of 61 years old and above (f=1) or 0.72%. The table further shows that the mainstream of the teachers are middle-aged adults.

Table 1.3
Educational Attainment of Teachers

Educational Attainment	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Bachelor's Degree Graduate	57	41.01

With Units in Master's Degree	47	33.81
Master's Degree Graduate	33	23.74
Doctorate Degree Graduate	2	1.44
Total	139	100.0%

Table 1.3 reveals that the highest numbers of teachers are bachelor's degree graduate (f=57) or 41.01%. The lowest numbers of teachers are doctorate degree graduate (f=2) or 1.44%.

Table 1.4
Teaching Position of Teachers

Teaching Position	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Teacher I	72	51.80
Teacher II	29	20.86
Teacher III/ SPED Teacher	38	27.34
Total	139	100.0%

It can be derived from the table 1.4 that most of the teachers' position is Teacher I (f=72) or 51.80, it was followed by Teacher III/ SPED Teacher (f=38) or 27.34%. The least of the teachers' position is Teacher II (f=29) or 20.86%.

Table 1.5
Teaching Experience of Teachers

Teaching Experience	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1-5 years	28	20.14
6-10 years	43	30.94
11-15 years	24	17.27
16 or more	44	31.65
Total	139	100.0%

As indicated to table 1.5, with regards to teachers' teaching experience, 20.14% have 1-5 years teaching experience (f=28), 30.94% have 6-10 years teaching experience (f=43), 17.27% have 11-15 years teaching experience (f=24), and 31.65% have 16 or more years of teaching experience (f=44).

Table 2.1
Teachers' Job Satisfaction in the Aspect of Work and Workplace

Teachers' Job Satisfaction in the Aspect of Work and Workplace	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Our school rules and procedures are appropriate and reasonable.	4.10	0.95	Satisfied
2. I like the people I work with.	4.21	0.89	Satisfied
3. My workmates are competent.	4.30	0.88	Very Satisfied
4. I like doing the things I do at work.	4.22	0.90	Very Satisfied
5. My duties and responsibilities are achievable.	4.24	0.88	Very Satisfied
6. I have the opportunity to take part in trainings, webinars, meetings and outreach activities.	4.17	0.83	Satisfied
7. I receive the information, tools and resources I need to do my job effectively.	4.11	0.88	Satisfied
8. I know what is expected of me at work.	4.22	0.82	Very Satisfied
9. I am allowed / encouraged to make decisions to solve problems for my students.	4.29	0.74	Very Satisfied
10. I know how to measure the quality of my work.	4.27	0.76	Very Satisfied
11. The people I work with cooperate as a team.	4.29	0.78	Very Satisfied
12. I have a safe workplace.	4.18	0.79	Satisfied
13. I would not consider leaving my job.	4.11	0.96	Satisfied
14. All employees have an equal opportunity to further their education.	4.28	0.83	Very Satisfied
15. I feel my job has value to the community.	4.57	0.72	Very Satisfied
SUMMATIVE MEAN	4.24	0.85	Very Satisfied

Legend: **5** [4.20-5.00] Very Satisfied
 4 [3.40-4.19] Satisfied
 3 [2.60-3.39] Neutral
 2 [1.80-2.59] Dissatisfied
 1 [1.00-1.79] Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.1 shows the teachers' job satisfaction in the aspect of work and workplace. Specifically, indicator 15 (M=4.57, SD=0.72) obtained the highest mean, implying that teachers are 'very satisfied' that their job has value to the community. Furthermore, indicator 1 (M=4.10, SD=0.95) yielded the lowest mean, which infer that the teachers are 'satisfied' that the schools' rules and procedures are appropriate and reasonable. Meanwhile, the rest of the indicators got a mean ranging from 4.11 to 4.30.

To sum up, the teachers' job satisfaction in the aspect of work and workplace (M=4.24, SD=0.85) is verbally interpreted as 'very satisfied'. Related to the study of Baluyos et al. (2019), they defined job satisfaction plays an essential role in the overall commitment and productivity of the school organization.

Table 2.2
Teachers' Job Satisfaction in the Aspect of Supervisor and Management

Teachers' Job Satisfaction in the Aspect of Supervisor and Management	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
16. My school has the right people and skills to do its work.	4.29	0.72	Very Satisfied
17. My school practices high standards and ethics.	4.14	0.79	Satisfied
18. My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.	4.18	0.81	Satisfied
19. My supervisor shows interest in my feelings and acknowledges my concerns.	3.97	0.85	Satisfied
20. My supervisor treats me with dignity and respect.	4.02	0.84	Satisfied
21. My school consistently demonstrates support for a diverse workforce.	4.14	0.75	Satisfied
22. My supervisor holds me and my co-workers accountable for performance.	4.08	0.77	Satisfied
23. I can rely on my supervisor.	3.88	0.85	Satisfied
SUMMATIVE MEAN	4.09	0.81	Satisfied

Legend: **5** [4.20-5.00] Very Satisfied
 4 [3.40-4.19] Satisfied
 3 [2.60-3.39] Neutral
 2 [1.80-2.59] Dissatisfied
 1 [1.00-1.79] Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.2 discloses the teachers' job satisfaction in the aspect of supervisor and management. Indicator 16 (M=4.29, SD=0.72) got the highest mean, entailing that the teachers are '*very satisfied*' that the school has the right people and skills to do its work. Moreover, indicator 23 (M=3.88, SD=0.85) gained the lowest mean, specifying that the teachers are '*satisfied*' that they can rely on their supervisor. Meanwhile, the rest of the indicators got a mean ranging from 3.97 to 4.18. To sum up, teachers' job satisfaction on the aspect of supervisor and management (M=4.09, SD=0.85) is verbally interpreted as '*satisfied*'.

Table 2.3
Teachers' Job Satisfaction in the Aspect of Benefits and Recognitions

Teachers' Job Satisfaction in the Aspect of Benefits and Recognitions	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
24. I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.	3.73	0.89	Satisfied
25. I am satisfied with the benefits I receive.	3.71	0.87	Satisfied
26. My working hours are fair.	3.78	0.92	Satisfied
27. I feel that the work I do is appreciated.	3.91	0.80	Satisfied

28. My performance evaluation provides me with meaningful information about my performance.	4.03	0.82	Satisfied
29. My amount of vacation is enough.	3.53	0.99	Satisfied
SUMMATIVE MEAN	3.78	0.90	Satisfied

Legend: 5 [4.20-5.00] Very Satisfied
4 [3.40-4.19] Satisfied
3 [2.60-3.39] Neutral
2 [1.80-2.59] Dissatisfied
1 [1.00-1.79] Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.3 displays the teachers' job satisfaction in the aspect of benefits and recognitions. Indicator 28 (M=4.03, SD=0.82) garnered the highest mean, signifying that the teachers are '*satisfied*' that their performance evaluation provides them with meaningful information about their performance. Deliberately, indicator 29 (M=3.53, SD=0.99) obtained the lowest mean, denoting that the teachers are also '*satisfied*' that the amount of their vacation is enough. It is noteworthy that all the indicators obtained a verbal interpretation of '*satisfied*'. Meanwhile, the rest of the indicators got a mean ranging from 3.71 to 3.91.

To sum up, the teachers' job satisfaction in the aspect of benefits and recognitions (M=3.78, SD=0.90) is verbally interpreted as '*satisfied*'. The result of this study is supported by the findings of Maqbool (2017) because job satisfaction affects students' performance, and educational improvement.

Table 2.4
Summary Table of Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction

Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Work and Workplace	4.24	0.85	Very Satisfied
Supervisor and Management	4.09	0.81	Satisfied
Benefits and Recognitions	3.78	0.90	Satisfied
SUMMATIVE MEAN	4.03	0.87	Satisfied

Legend: 5 [4.20-5.00] Very Satisfied
4 [3.40-4.19] Satisfied
3 [2.60-3.39] Neutral
2 [1.80-2.59] Dissatisfied
1 [1.00-1.79] Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.4 outlines the summary of teachers' level of job satisfaction in the three aspects. The aspect of work and workplace (M=4.24, SD=0.85) obtained the highest mean, it was followed by the aspect of supervisor and management (M=4.09, SD=0.81). The aspect on benefits and recognitions (M=3.78, SD=0.90) yielded the lowest mean. As a conclusion, teachers' job satisfaction (M=4.03, SD=0.87) is verbally interpreted as '*satisfied*'.

Table 3
Teachers' Degree of Burnout

Teachers' Degree of Burnout	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I feel emotionally exhausted because of my work	3.52	1.60	At least once a month
2. I feel worn out at the end of a working day	3.73	1.84	Several times a month
3. I feel tired as soon as I get up in the morning and see a new working day stretched out in front of me	2.77	1.70	At least once a month
4. I can easily understand the actions of my colleagues/ supervisors	5.35	1.75	Several times a week
5. I get the feeling that I treat some clients/colleagues impersonally, as if they were objects	1.88	1.54	At least a few times a year
6. Working with people the whole day is stressful for me	2.23	1.65	At least a few times a year
7. I deal with other people's problems successfully	3.55	1.81	At least once a month
8. I feel burned out because of my work	2.81	1.68	At least once a month
9. I feel that I influence other people positively through my work	5.01	1.80	Once a week
10. I have become more insensitive to people since I have started doing this job	2.14	1.69	At least a few times a year
11. I'm afraid that my work makes me emotionally harder	2.41	1.56	At least a few times a year
12. I feel full of energy	5.56	1.49	Several times a week
13. I feel frustrated by my work	2.32	1.49	At least a few times a year
14. I get the feeling that I work too hard	3.41	1.91	At least once a month
15. I'm not really interested in what is going on with many of my colleagues	2.01	1.39	At least a few times a year
16. Being in direct contact with people at work is too stressful	2.28	1.54	At least a few times a year
17. I find it easy to build a relaxed atmosphere in my working environment	4.97	1.88	Once a week
18. I feel stimulated when I been working closely with my colleagues	4.63	2.01	Once a week

19. I have achieved many rewarding objectives in my work	4.01	1.92	Several times a month
20. I feel that I'm completely puzzled, not knowing what to do.	2.52	1.50	At least a few times a year
21. In my work I am very relaxed when dealing with emotional problems	3.86	2.00	Several times a month
22. I have the feeling that my colleagues blame me for some of their problems	1.58	1.10	Never
SUMMATIVE MEAN	3.30	2.07	At least once a month

Legend:

- 7 [6.16-7.00] Every day
- 6 [5.30-6.15] Several times a week
- 5 [4.44-5.29] Once a week
- 4 [3.58-4.43] Several times a month
- 3 [2.72-3.57] At least once a month
- 2 [1.86-2.71] At least a few times a year
- 1 [1.00-1.85] Never

Table 3 reveals the teachers' degree of burnout. Indicator 12 (M=5.56, SD=1.49) obtained the highest mean, indicating that teachers felt full of energy '*several times a week*'. On the other hand, indicator 22 (M=1.58, SD=1.10) yielded the lowest mean suggesting that teachers '*never*' felt that their colleagues blame them for some of their problems. Meanwhile, the rest of the indicators got a mean ranging from 1.88 to 5.35.

As a whole, the teachers' degree of burnout (M=3.30, SD=2.07) is verbally interpreted or frequently felt '*at least once a month*'. In connection to the study of Whitehead (2001), he defined burnout as a state of physical and emotional depletion resulting from conditions of work; definitely this state must be avoided.

Teachers' Stress Preventative Coping Strategy

Table 4
Teachers' Stress Preventative Coping Strategy

Teachers' Stress Preventative Coping Strategy	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I can trust my own judgments.	3.96	0.67	Agree
2. I know how to pick the right coping strategy for the right situation.	4.02	0.58	Agree
3. I know how to make social situations more comfortable.	3.99	0.64	Agree
4. I know how to think about situations in a positive way.	4.12	0.63	Agree
5. I see problems as opportunities to learn and grow.	4.25	0.70	Strongly Agree

6. When new information comes my way, I can recognize when it will be important to me.	4.08	0.65	Agree
7. I use humor to keep difficulties from becoming stressful.	3.99	0.83	Agree
8. My sense of humor keeps my stress level under control.	4.06	0.67	Agree
9. I can communicate my needs to others.	4.04	0.73	Agree
10. I can handle stressful situations.	3.96	0.72	Agree
11. I can recognize when someone is about to become unhappy with me.	3.93	0.61	Agree
12. I am able to ask for emotional support.	3.91	0.76	Agree
13. I believe the difficulties I am facing will not last forever.	4.44	0.65	Strongly Agree
14. I know how to make others feel comfortable.	4.10	0.63	Agree
15. I am able to recognize when I need to take action to avoid causing stress in my life.	4.07	0.54	Agree
16. I have others to call upon when needed.	4.14	0.71	Agree
17. I have goals that keep me focused.	4.32	0.67	Strongly Agree
18. I have mutually supportive relationships.	4.30	0.67	Strongly Agree
19. I can learn new tasks.	4.43	0.60	Strongly Agree
20. I know my own limits.	4.33	0.67	Strongly Agree
21. I am able to reduce my daily demand level by planning ahead.	4.14	0.59	Agree
22. If I fail in one situation, I know I can still succeed in other situations.	4.36	0.68	Strongly Agree
23. I know I can't be all things to all people.	4.16	0.69	Agree
24. I can adapt to change.	4.29	0.61	Strongly Agree
25. When problems come up in one area they don't affect my overall happiness.	3.96	0.74	Agree
26. I do not want to trade my life for anyone else's life.	4.14	0.82	Strongly Agree
27. I am able to prevent stress by having clear values in my life.	4.33	0.67	Strongly Agree
28. I know how to learn from my mistakes.	4.39	0.67	Strongly Agree
29. I accept my imperfections.	4.52	0.62	Strongly Agree
30. I am able to use constructive criticism.	4.16	0.69	Agree
31. I know when I need to "go with the flow" to prevent a situation from becoming stressful.	4.16	0.63	Agree

32. I can find the bright side to most situations.	4.23	0.64	Strongly Agree
SUMMATIVE MEAN	4.16	0.69	Agree

Legend: 5 [4.20-5.00] Strongly Agree
 4 [3.40-4.19] Agree
 3 [2.60-3.39] Undecided
 2 [1.80-2.59] Disagree
 1 [1.00-1.79] Strongly Disagree

Table 4 depicts the teachers' stress preventative coping strategy. Indicator 29 (M=4.52, SD=0.62) obtained the highest mean, indicating that teachers are 'strongly agree' that their stress preventative coping strategy is to accept their imperfections. On the other hand, indicator 12 (M=3.91, SD=0.76) yielded the lowest mean implying that teachers are 'agree' that their stress preventative coping strategy is to ask for emotional support. Meanwhile, the rest of the indicators got a mean ranging from 3.93 to 4.44. As a conclusion, the teachers' stress preventative coping strategy (M=4.16, SD=0.69) is verbally interpreted as 'agree'.

Relationship between Teachers' Demographic Profile and their Level of Job Satisfaction, Degree of Burnout, and Stress Preventative Coping Strategy

Table 5
Chi-square Test Results

	sex	age group	educational background	teaching position	teaching experience
Level of Job Satisfaction	0.297	0.029*	0.307	0.330	0.269
Degree of Burnout	0.322	0.085	0.142	0.266	0.185
Stress Preventative Coping Strategy	0.333	0.152	0.316	0.232	0.088

Legend: * - Significant at 0.05 level
 ** - Significant at 0.01 level

Table 5 illustrates that the teachers' age group is positively correlated to the level of job satisfaction. It means that the change in teachers' age group do significantly correlate with the increase or decrease of these indicators of Level of Job Satisfaction.

The findings of the current study is not in consonance with the study of Baluyos et al. (2019), their study revealed that teachers who are satisfied with their teaching assignments or jobs were equipped with a Masters' degree, and with an average teaching experience of nine years.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: 1) Out of 139 respondents majority of them were composed of female, in the age group of 26-30 years old and 36-40 years old, have bachelor's degree, holds Teacher I position, and have 16 or more years of teaching experience; 2) The teachers' job satisfaction ($M=4.03$, $SD=0.87$) is verbally interpreted as '*satisfied*'; 3) The teachers' degree of burnout ($M=3.30$, $SD=2.07$) is verbally interpreted or frequently felt '*at least once a month*'; 4) The teachers' stress preventative coping strategy ($M=4.16$, $SD=0.69$) is verbally interpreted as '*agree*'; and 5) Teachers' age group is positively correlated to the level of job satisfaction.

Recommendations

Grounded on the results and discussions, the following recommendations are hereby offered: a) The school environment should build a culture that displays the amount of gratification and promote social and emotional competency to all the employees. Capitalize intangible factors like communication, boosting confidence, respect for self and others, optimism and hope, trust, problem-solving and coping skills, and sense of purpose and meaning; b) To prevent the teachers' burnout, schools should keep track on teachers' well-being and offer instructional, physical, mental, spiritual and emotional support throughout the school year; c) Schools should make meaningful partnership with mental health experts like guidance counsellors or behaviour support specialists to ensure that teachers get the awareness and help they need; d) School heads should include the job satisfaction, degree of burnout, and stress preventative coping strategy in Learning Circle Sessions or In-Service Training, so teachers will improve their understanding of mental health conditions and escalate access to various healthcare; e) For further research, it is recommended to do a longitudinal study about the effects of Mental Health and Psychosocial to teachers' performance; and f) Future researchers may do similar studies emphasizing the direct effect of teachers' level of job satisfaction, degree of burnout, and stress preventative coping strategy to students' academic performance.

Dissemination and Advocacy Plans

Schools may adapt the proposed project entitled E.M.B.R.A.C.E. (**E**mpowering **M**ental Health and Psychosocial Services **B**y **R**aising **A**wareness and **C**onducting **E**vidence-based activities). The main objective of this dissemination, utilization, and advocacy strategy is to raise awareness about Mental Health and Psychosocial Supports and Services through conducting webinars and evidence-based activities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To address the possible ethical concerns that could emanate from the conduct of the research and discussions, the researcher furnished a permit to conduct the study from the School Head of Kasiglahan Village Elementary School. The researcher also presented the research proposal and findings to the Master Teachers and School Head for cross checking of the data. The researcher also secured a free prior and informed consent from the respondents of the study, and made sure that the data they had provided will be treated with utmost confidentiality and anonymity. The researcher presented the authentic research findings without any falsification and fabrication.

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REFERENCES

- Baluyos, G., Rivera, H. and Baluyos, E. (2019) Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Work Performance. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, **7**, 206-221. DOI: 10.4236/jss.2019.78015
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, W.L. (2007). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_609332/objava_105202/fajlovi/Creswell.pdf
- Croom, D. B, (2003). Teacher burnout in agricultural education. North Carolina State University. *Journal of Agricultural Education*.
<https://doi.org/10.5032/jae.2003.02001>
- Division Memorandum No. 371, s. 2021. Convergence on Oplan Balik Eskwela 2021.
<https://depedrizal.ph/2021/08/26/division-memorandum-no-371-s-2021/>
- Division Memorandum No. 380, s. 2020. Online Monitoring and Validation of Oplan Balik Eskwela (OBE), Schools Readiness and Opening of Classes for S.Y. 2020-2021. <https://depedrizal.ph/2020/09/28/division-memorandum-no-380-s-2020/>
- Division Memorandum No. 434, s. 2022, titled "Monitoring of Opening of Classes, Implementation of K-12 Basic Education Curriculum, and School Governance and Operations for School Year 2022-2023". <https://depedrizal.ph/2022/08/19/division-memorandum-no-434-s-2022/>
- Etikan I, & Bala K. (2017). Sampling and sampling methods. *Biom Biostat Int J*. 2017;5(6):215?217. DOI: 10.15406/bbij.2017.05.00149
- Maqbool, S. (2017) Interrelationship between Collective Teacher Efficacy and Job Satisfaction of Teachers at Secondary Schools. *NUML Journal of Critical Inquiry*, **15**, 180-196.
<https://search.proquest.com/docview/2011249258?accountid=149218>

- Maslach, C., Jackson, S. E., & Leiter, M. P. (1996). *Maslach Burnout Inventory Manual* (3rd ed.). Mountain View, CA: CPP, Inc.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277816643_The_Maslach_Burnout_Inventory_Manual
- McCarthy, C. J., Lambert, R. G., O'Donnell, M., & Melendres, L. T. (2009). The Relation of Elementary Teachers' Experience, Stress, and Coping Resources to Burnout Symptoms. *The Elementary School Journal*, 109(3), 282-300.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/592308>
- McCarthy, C. J., Lambert, R. G., & Reiser, J. (2014). Vocational concerns of elementary teachers: Stress, job satisfaction, and occupational commitment. *Journal of Employment Counseling*, 51(2), 59–74. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2161-1920.2014.00042.x>
- Mooney, J. M. (2018). The relationship between stress, preventive coping resources, and burnout among elementary teachers. Eastern Illinois University.
<https://thekeep.eiu.edu/theses/3701>
- National Association of County and City Health Officials (NACCHO) (2012).
https://www.phf.org/events/Pages/National_Association_of_County_and_City_Health_Officials_NACCHO_Annual_2012.aspx
- Pressley, T. (2021). Factors Contributing to Teacher Burnout During COVID-19. *Educational Researcher*, 50(5), 325–327.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X211004138>
- Sousa, V., Driessnack, M., & Mendes, I. (2007). An overview of research designs relevant to nursing: Part 1 quantitative research designs. *Rev. Latino-Am. Enfermagem* 15 (3). DOI: 10.1590/s0104-11692007000300022
- Talidong, K. B., & Toquero, C. (2020). Philippine Teachers' Practices to Deal with Anxiety Amid COVID -19. *Journal of Loss and Trauma: International Perspective on Stress and Coping*, 573-579. DOI: 10.1080/15325024.2020.1759225
- Whitehead, A. J. (2001). *Teacher Burnout: A Study of Occupational Stress and Burnout in New Zealand School Teachers*. <http://hdl.handle.net/10179/2083>
- Yale School of Public Health. (2020, 8 21). Mental Health Among students, Teachers and Staff. <https://ysph.yale.edu/public-health-research-and-practice/interdepartmental-foci/infectious-diseases/covid/reopening-information/guidance-for-reopening-schools/mental-health-issues/>